

The beaver, a pioneer hydrosystem engineer in the Plan Nord area

Photo: Françoise Gervais

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The North American Beaver

(Castor canadensis)

- Well known for dam and lodge building capacities.
- A controversial species:
 - a landscape designer
 - a corner stone of the ecosystems
 - a nuisance for human infrastructures.
- A neglected engineer in the Plan Nord.

A

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Profile of the Beaver

- Current position
- Education and experience
- Projects and achievements
- Connections and contacts
- Skills and expertise (tote bag)

Current position

- Head, stream impoundment for USA and Canada.
- Number of staffs
 - North America: 6-12 million (Naiman 1988)
 - Quebec: >700,000 (Lafond et al. 2003)
 - Plan Nord area: 200,000 ?

Education and experience

- Birthdate: 50,000,000 BP. Emergence of the beaver.
- Post-glaciation kinder garden of the Plan Nord area: 9,000 BP-1600.
- Hudson Bay's Company highschool: 1670-1900.
 - Special training on trap avoidance to overcome extinction.
 - The first resource of interest to European settlers in the Plan Nord area.
- University of Life : Since 1900. Specialty: exponential population recovery.

Projects & Achievements

1. Intensive damming in Duparquet (Abitibi)

- A 80-km² research and teaching forest
- 93 km of streams
- 57 km converted to ponds by 458 dams.
- Average pond size: 0,64 ha.
- Dam length: 0-437m.
- Only 3% of the forest was flooded.
- Sustainable management!

Carte des barrages de castor (actifs et inactifs) et des milieux humides dynamisés par le castor sur le territoire de la Forêt d'enseignement et de recherche du lac Duparquet en 2006

Typical stream of Duparquet with chains of dams

Mud is an important component of dams in the Abitibi Claybelt, increasing dams durability

Projects and Achievements

2. Benchmarking for evaluation of human footprint left by timber floating structures in the boreal transition zone

- Use of waterways by humans for log transportation from 1850-1985 has heavily altered hydrosystems in the Meridional Laurentians.
- Beaver provides a reference for ecological restoration by National Park managers. Three indicators:
 - Number of dams /km²
 - Average pond size
 - Duration of successional stages.

Comparison of densities (per ha) of timber floating impoundments with beaver ponds.

La Mauricie National Park of Canada		
	Number	Density (nb/km ²)
Beaver	580	1.081
Timber	29	0.054
Total	609	

Comparisons of the areas of beaver ponds Vs timber floating impoundments in La Mauricie National Park

Chabot and Darveau 2011

Projects and Achievements

3. Improving aquatic bird habitat in boreal landscapes

Importance of the Plan Nord area to waterfowl showing preference for beaver ponds

- Total waterfowl in the Plan Nord
 - 1,2 million breeding pairs
 - 30 species

- Beaver-associated species

- American Black Duck (36% of 910,000 world breeding individuals are in the Plan Nord area)
- Canada Goose (13% of the 5,570,000)
- Hooded Merganser (21% of 350,000)
- Ringed-necked Duck (10% of 2,000,000)

Contacts

-
- All connections (>500)
 - Tags
 - Dependent wildlife and ecosystem processes (>500)
 - Trappers (>500)*
 - Aboriginal (>500)
 - Others (200)
 - Scientists (300)
 - Governments and Institutions using beaver as an emblems (>30)

** Most of the Plan Nord area has a legal status of Beaver Reserves with exclusive trapping rights for aboriginal people since early 1900s.*

Other Skills and Expertise

Road damage

50% of culverts filled by beaver in Abitibi
(Tremblay 2010)

Geneviève Tremblay

Damage can be overcome with an array of rocks

Marcel Darveau

Tree felling

Marcel Darveau

Riparian management

Pierre Dulude

Other Skills and Expertise: climate change

- Carbon storage/emissions vary with successional stage.
- Beaver predicted to benefit from climate change in the Plan Nord area in the next 50 years:
 - range expansion to the North
 - density increase in current range

Fig. 4 Predicted changes in (1) beaver density (colonies km⁻²) with a 10% increase in climate variables (climate sensitivity), (2) climate from present to the year 2055 (climate change) based on the CGCM1 GA1 model, and (3) beaver density change across Québec from present to the year 2055 (density change) based on three climatic variables with best-fit models: (a) potential evapotranspiration (PET), (b) average maximum March–April–May–July–August temperature (T_{\maxmam}), and (c) average maximum June–July–August temperature (T_{\maxja}). White areas indicate regions not inhabited by beavers at present (column 1; climate sensitivity) and in the future (column 3; density change). Projection of future range limits is based on matching the current isotherm delineating the northern most location of beaver at present, then using the GCM projection of the location of this isotherm in 2055 [(a.3) PET = 200 mm, (b.3) T_{\maxmam} = –1.4°C, (c.3) T_{\maxja} = 15.2°C].

In summary

The beaver:

- A pioneer engineer in the Plan Nord Area.
- A corner stone species for ecosystems.
- A resource to trappers.
- A champion of sustainability!

Literature cited

- Chabot, A. and M. Darveau. 2011. Comparaison de l'altération des hydrosystèmes par le castor et la drave dans les parcs nationaux de la Mauricie et de la Jacques-Cartier. Canards Illimités Canada, Rapport technique Q17, Québec, Québec.
- Jarema, S. J., J. Samson, B. J. McGill, and M. M. Humphries. 2009. Variation in abundance across a species' range predicts climate change responses in the range interior will exceed those at the edge: a case study with North American beaver. *Global Change Biology* 15:508-522.
- Lafond, R. and C. Pilon. 2004. Abondance du castor (*Castor canadensis*) au Québec - Bilan d'un programme d'inventaire aérien. *Le Naturaliste canadien* 128:43-51.
- Lemelin, L. V. and M. Darveau. 2008. Les milieux humides du parc national du Canada de la Mauricie: cartographie en vue d'une surveillance de l'intégrité écologique. Canards Illimités Canada, Rapport technique Q11, Québec.
- Lemelin, L. V., M. Darveau, L. Imbeau, and D. Bordage. 2010. Wetland use and selection by breeding waterbirds in the boreal forest of Quebec, Canada. *Wetlands* 30:321-332.
- Meunier, G., M. C. LeBlanc, M. Darveau, C. M. Bouchard, and L. Imbeau. 2009. Les milieux d'eau profonde, humides et forestiers riverains de la Forêt d'enseignement et de recherche du lac Duparquet. Canards Illimités Canada, Rapport technique Q16, Québec, Québec.
- Naiman, R. J., C. A. Johnston, and J. C. Kelley. 1988. Alteration of North American streams by beaver. *BioScience* 38:753-762.
- Tremblay, G. 2010. Caractérisation des paramètres de l'habitat du castor qui favorisent l'utilisation des ponceaux comme site de construction de barrage. Mem. M.Sc. Université du Québec en Abitibi-Témiscamingue, Rouyn-Noranda.